

Oral Language Development and Language Proficiency Among Grade Seven Students

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Abstract. The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of Oral Language Development on the language proficiency of grade seven students. The study employed a quasi-experimental research design, specifically a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. This design was chosen because the study involved intact groups of learners, making random assignment impractical. The research was conducted at Sta. Cruz National School, Sta. Cruz South District, Division of Davao Del Sur, involving 91 grade seven students. Of these, 46 were assigned to section A as the controlled group, and 45 to section B as the experimental group. Both sections were homogeneous in composition, with students having identical grades. Findings from the study revealed that the implementation of oral language development significantly improved the language competency of seventh-grade students. Moreover, there was a notable difference in the post-test scores between the controlled and experimental groups, indicating the effectiveness of the intervention.

KEY WORDS

1. Oral Language 2. Language proficiency 3. Development

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1. Introduction

Learners frequently express frustration with experiencing anxiety during the language acquisition process. They assert that they have a mental block hindering their ability to acquire proficiency in the language. According to research findings, it has been established that around one-third of individuals engaged in language learning encounter a certain degree of a psychological state known as language anxiety. Hence, the concept of language anxiety has garnered considerable attention and has been the subject of extensive academic research in recent times. This element is widely recognized as having significant influence on the process of language acquisition. This hinders learners' ability to achieve their objectives and hinders the successful attainment of language proficiency in the target language (Jackson, 2019). Learners may experience anxiety in many different aspects of the teaching and learning process, that includes the complexity of the language, public speaking in the presence of fellow learners, the language class itself, the behavior of their peers, test-taking, and interactions with native speakers of the language being learned, among others. Hence, the occurrence of language anxiety may arise when learners encounter several negative experiences within a language learning environment (Liu, 2020). Several researchers have given definitions of anxiety in the con-

text of language anxiety. Language anxiety can be described as a comprehensive set of self-perceptions, beliefs, emotions, and behaviors that are associated with the process of learning a language in a classroom setting, caused by the distinctive nature of the language learning experience. Furthermore, language anxiety can be characterized as a state of unease and concern that is clearly linked to situations involving the use of a second language, including activities such as speaking, listening, and acquiring language abilities (Wu, 2020). It is believed that anxiety can exert negative effects, leading to the development of physiological and behavioral symptoms among individuals engaged in the process of learning. For instance, it has the potential to cause changes in learners' behavior, such as a decreased motivation to engage in studying and difficulties in maintaining focus (Yan, 2020). In Vietnam, Numerous research have demonstrated the commonality of language anxiety among those who are learning the Vietnamese language. A research investigation was conducted among a sample of university students in Vietnam, finding that 68% of students indicated experiencing moderate to high levels of language anxiety during their utilization of the English language. The anxiety experienced by individuals can be related to a range of circumstances, such as the fear of committing errors, a lack in confidence, and the pressure to excel academically (Maningo, 2020). In the Division of Davao del Sur particularly in Sta. Cruz National School, no study has been conducted to look for language anxiety and how it affects the language proficiency of Grade 7 students. Thus, the researcher finds it appropriate and timely to conduct this study to propose a plan of action on how (name of school) further improves the language proficiency of Grade 7 students,

especially nowadays where students are more vulnerable to many factors that hinder language development.

1.1. Review of Related Literature—This section summarizes key readings and research relevant to language proficiency and language anxiety among grade seven students.

1.1.1. Language Proficiency—Language proficiency encompasses the ability to effectively use a language in various contexts, including reading, writing, speaking, and listening, as well as cultural understanding (Kamrul Hasan, 2020). Several factors influence language proficiency:

Exposure: Frequent exposure to oral and written language enhances vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension (Fuchsen, 2019). **Age of Acquisition:** Early language learning typically results in higher proficiency, though adults can also achieve high proficiency with dedication (MacGregor, 2020). **Cultural Background:** Diverse linguistic and cultural backgrounds can either facilitate or complicate language learning (Li, 2020). **Educational Environment:** Quality teaching, resources, and supportive teachers are crucial (Alderson, 2020; Larsson, 2020). **Cognitive Abilities:** Strong cognitive skills like memory and problem-solving aid language acquisition (Light, 2019). Educational institutions play a significant role by providing structured language training and practice opportunities. High language proficiency correlates with academic success across various subjects (Woodrow, 2020) and is valued in the global economy for roles in translation, business, and diplomacy (IIE, 2019).

Language proficiency also aids cultural integration, helping immigrants engage socially and access opportunities in their host countries (Ellis, 2020). However, challenges such as pronunciation, grammar, vocabulary, and socio-cultural issues can hinder proficiency (Hakuta, 2020). Effective strategies include immersive programs, interactive learning, and digital re-

sources (Pokay, 2020; Takahshi, 2019).

1.1.2. Language Anxiety—Language anxiety, or communication apprehension, is the fear or unease when using a second language. It manifests as fear of speaking, writing, or social interaction in the new language (Gregersen, 2019). Key factors include:

Fear of Errors: Anxiety about making mistakes and being judged by peers can deter language practice (Hashemi, 2019). **Cultural Factors:** Collectivist cultures may experience higher anxiety due to fear of losing social standing (Jones, 2020). **Evaluation Anxiety:** Fear of negative assessment by teachers or peers can increase stress (Cheng, 2021). **Low Self-Confidence:** Lack of confidence in language skills can lead to avoidance of participation (Ariyanti, 2020). **Instructional Methods:** Emphasizing grammar drills can increase anxiety, while interactive methods can reduce it (De-waele, 2020). Language anxiety can impair comprehension, production, and overall language proficiency, leading to cognitive overload and reduced motivation (Young, 2020). Effective approaches to mitigate anxiety include supportive teaching, constructive feedback, and creating a non-threatening learning environment (Tittle, 2020).

Technological advancements in language learning, such as online platforms and virtual classrooms, offer engaging ways to reduce anxiety and enhance proficiency (Takahshi, 2019). Addressing language anxiety is essential for both second-language learners and native speakers, particularly in contexts like public speaking (Scovel, 2020).

This literature review highlights the importance of understanding and addressing the various factors affecting language proficiency and anxiety to improve language learning outcomes for grade seven students.

1.2. Synthesis—The literature review presented above provides an overview of the perspectives and viewpoints of various authors re-

garding the impact of language anxiety in language proficiency that can lead to improved academic performance of the students. While some authors share similar ideas, there are also contrasting statements. These statements will serve as a guide for the researcher in conducting her own study, forming conclusions, and making recommendations. Additionally, the literature review will serve as a framework for the researcher to follow throughout the research process. It will also serve as a reference for the researcher to support and justify any findings that arise from the statistical analysis and interpretation.

1.3. Theoretical/Conceptual Framework—Models or theories of second/foreign language learning give valuable insight into language anxiety, enabling its recognition. The following second language acquisition theories are discussed: The Affective Filter Hypothesis of Krashen (1982) and the Theory of Foreign Language Anxiety of Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope. In the matter of second language learning, Krashen's Affective Filter Hypothesis (1982) is an important idea. This approach emphasizes the relationship between emotive elements and the process of second language learning. The affective components, according to Krashen (1982), are emotional characteristics that can be characterized as follows: 1) motivation, 2) self-confidence, and 3) anxiety. These variables can impact learning indirectly by blocking input from reaching the brain's language acquisition apparatus. This idea clarifies the connection between emotional characteristics and the success or failure of second language acquisition. For instance, when the emotional filter is heightened, students may sense worry, stress, and a lack of self-confidence, all of which inhibit their achievement. Low filters, on the other hand, do not cause anxiety, allowing language learners to readily comprehend material. The significance of this hypothesis in pedagogy stems from the fact that the concept of affective

filter presents a language instructor in a new light, namely, as someone who can effectively facilitate input and make it understandable in a low-anxiety situation, where an appropriate classroom environment can be created. In other words, a language teacher can reduce his or her students' anxiety by focusing on the message, ignoring the form, and not insisting on early output until he or she determines that the pupils are ready. By employing this approach, it is anticipated that English proficiency will increase since input will be increased, the filter will be lowered, and students will not be frightened to participate in class exercises. In their well-known research, Horwitz, Horwitz, and Cope (1986) characterize foreign language anxiety as "a separate complex construct of self-perceptions, beliefs, attitudes, and behaviors associated to classroom language acquisition resulting from the distinctiveness of the language learning process" (p. 128). According to them, anxiety linked with learning a foreign language is a situation-specific form resulting from the peculiarity of learning a foreign language, and not a generic anxiety transferred to language acquisition. They demonstrate their theory by watching language learners during the teaching process in language classes and by receiving feedback from language learners who are enrolled in classes. This theory posits that other aca-

demical disciplines of study do not need the same level of self-concept and self-expression as foreign language acquisition, hence distinguishing this sort of worry from other academic worries. When studying a foreign language, learners who excelled in other courses suffered worry. Numerous research embraced this hypothesis and offered data to support it. MacIntyre and Gardner (1989) employed nine anxiety scales to examine the relationship between anxiety dimensions and several measures of learning. They discovered that foreign language anxiety is significantly related to foreign language competency, but general anxiety had no correlation with foreign language proficiency. Similarly, Chen and Chang (2004) feel that foreign language worry is a situation-specific anxiety perspective. In their paper, neither test features nor academic learning history were identified as determinants of foreign language anxiety, indicating that it is a distinct sort of worry. These findings supported the hypothesis that anxiety linked with learning a foreign language is a distinct sort of anxiety resulting from the uniqueness of language acquisition. The conceptual framework of this research shows the independent variable which is the Language Anxiety. The dependent variable is the Language Proficiency of Grade 7 Students is affected by the independent variable.

1.4. Statement of the Problem—The general purpose of this study is to look into the effect of Oral Language Development on the lan-

guage proficiency of the grade seven students. Specifically, this research study aims to answer the following research objectives.

- (1) What are the pretest scores of the pre-school learners both controlled and experimental groups?
- (2) What are the posttest scores of the pre-school learners in both controlled and experimental group?
- (3) Is there significant difference between the post scores of the controlled and experimental groups?
- (4) What is the magnitude of effect of oral language development on the language proficiency of the grade seven learners?

1.5. —

Fig. 1. Schematic Diagram Showing the Flow of the Study.

Null Hypotheses The null hypothesis in this study will be tested at 0.05 level of significance. H01. There is no significant difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups. H02. Oral language development has no effect on the language proficiency of the grade seven learners. The Null Hypothesis in this study will be tested at 0.05 level of significance. HO1. The language anxiety has no significant relationship in the language proficiency of Grade 7 students.

1.6. *Significance of the Study*—The following are considered beneficiaries of the study. DepEd Officials. The result of this study will reveal the level of impact of language anxiety and how it affects the language proficiency of Grade 7 students Moreover, this research will provide the foundation for DepEd Officials to organize a range of seminars and pertinent training programs across multiple fields on the implementation of variety of teaching methodology, particularly in addressing the language anxiety of Grade 7 students. School Administrators. The findings of this study are beneficial to the school head of Sta. Cruz National School. They school head can utilize the vital information from this research study to implement variety of teaching methodology that will directly affect

the language proficiency of Grade 7 student. As instructional leaders, school heads are tasked to implement different instructions to promote teachers' pedagogy in realizing the learning institutions' goals, missions, and visions. Teachers. The findings of this research study are helpful to teachers of Sta. Cruz National School as to what strategies they will employ to decrease the language anxiety and increase the language proficiency of Grade 7 students, especially during this time, where students are vulnerable to many factors that hinder students language development. Future Researchers. The findings of this study may encourage them to conduct similar studies in other areas. This study serves as an additional source of reference and inquiries for their investigation relative to the present study.

1.7. *Definition of Terms*—To make this study comprehensive, the following terms are operationally and conceptually defined. Language Proficiency. Refers to an individual's ability to use a specific language effectively and accurately in various contexts, such as speaking, listening, reading, and writing (Andrade, 2019). Grade 7 Students. Refers to the Grade 7 students in the Philippines, part of the K-12 education system, are typically 12 to 13 years old. This marks the beginning of their junior

high school education (Department of Education, 2023).

2. Method

This chapter discusses the researcher method, the research design, the place and time, the research instruments, test construction and validation, scaling, data gathering procedure and the data analysis.

2.1. Research Design—This study makes use of the quasi experimental research design which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This design is represented as follows:

- 01 Pretest of the experimental group
- 02 Posttest of the experimental group
- 03 Pretest of the controlled group
- 04 Posttest of the controlled group
- Non-random assignment of subjects
- X Treatment applied in the experimental group

2.2. Research Respondents—This study will be conducted in Sta. Cruz National School, Sta Cruz South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 91 grade seven students – 46 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 45 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

Distribution of Respondents

Subjects	Section	No. of Pupils
1	Section A	46
2	Section B	45
Total		91

2.3. Research Instrument—This study will utilize the new normal learning modality. It is a blended learning where teacher gave module at the same meet the learners online but adhering to the protocols of Inter-agency Task Force (IATF). The researcher has to meet the learners on line for a follow up session of what has been printed in the module. The pre and post-

performance test consist of a 45 –item test will eventually determine the language proficiency of the respondents. The pretest will be administered to all subjects prior to the treatment. The pretest will be very helpful to assess the effect of oral language development on the language

proficiency of the grade seven students. On the hand, post test will be administered to measure the effect of the treatment. To determine the language proficiency of the grade seven students, the following continuum will be used based on DepEd rating system..

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
89 - 95	4	Proficient	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and can transfer them independently through authentic performance tasks.
82 - 88	3	Approaching Proficiency	The student at this level has developed the fundamental knowledge and skills and core understandings and, with little guidance from the teacher and/or with some assistance from peers, can transfer these understandings through authentic performance tasks.
75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

Interval Scale and Performance Levels

Interval	Scale	Level	Criteria
96 and above	5	Advanced	The student at this level exceeds the core requirements in terms of knowledge, skills and understandings and can transfer them automatically and flexibly through authentic performance tasks.
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75 - 81	2	Developing	The student at this level possesses the minimum knowledge and skills and core understandings but needs help throughout the performance of authentic tasks.
Below 75	1	Beginning	The student at this level struggles with his/her understanding; prerequisite and fundamental knowledge and/or skills have not been acquired or developed adequately to aid understanding.

2.4. *Data Gathering Procedure*—At the outset of data gathering procedure, the researcher will draft a letter seeking for permission that this research study be conducted were

sent to the Schools Division Superintendent of Davao Sur, Dr. Nelson Lopez, CESO V and the school principal of Sta. Cruz National High School. While letters seeking for permission

Task	Jan 2023	April 2023	May 2023	June 2023	July 2023	July 2023	Aug 2023	Aug 2023	July 2024
Title Defense	■								
Outline Defense		■							
Validation of Questionnaire			■						
Conduct of the Study				■					
Retrieval of Questionnaire					■				
Interpretation and Analysis						■			
Final Defense							■		
Incorporation of Comments and Suggestions							■		
Seeking the signature of Panel Members								■	
Graduation Day									

Fig. 2. Gantt Chart

were delivered to the Schools Division Superintendent and the school principal concerned, the researcher constructed a questionnaire and have it validated by the experts preferably the experts of the study. After permission has been granted that this study be conducted in Sta. Cruz National School and after the research questionnaire has been thoroughly examined by the expert validators, the researcher will administer pretest to both controlled and experimental class and eventually commences her experiment. After three weeks of experimentation, the researcher will administer posttest to both

sections. Scores of the subjects will be submitted to the statistician for statistical computation after which the researcher will make analysis and interpretation on the data gathered.

2.5. *Data Analysis*—The following statistical tools will be used in the analysis and interpretation the responses in this study. Mean will be used to describe the language proficiency level of the grade seven students in both pretest and posttest scores. Eta square will be used to measure the magnitude of effect of the oral language development of the language proficiency of the grade seven students.

3. Results and Discussion

This chapter presents the discussion of the problems in this study. They are discussed thoroughly, analyzed and interpreted under the following headings and sequence: Pre-test Scores of the Learners, Post-test Scores of the Learners and the Significant Relationship of the pre-tests and Post-tests Scores.

3.1. *Pre-Test Score of Learners*—Table 1 disclosed the pre-test scores of the grade

seven students. The controlled group got the mean of 23.5 or Beginning while the experimental group got the mean of 30.5 or Beginning.

Table 1: Pre-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	46	23.5	52.2	Beginning
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	45	30.5	67.8	Beginning

It can be gleaned from the table that during pre-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group although both belongs Beginning level. This finding is congruent to the idea of Kamrul Hasan (2020) who said that Language competency includes an individual’s capacity to employ a specific language with efficacy and precision across diverse settings. The concept of language proficiency comprises a range of abilities, including reading,

writing, speaking, and listening skills, as well as cultural understanding and communication competence (Kamrul Hasan, 2020). Language proficiency cannot be overlooked. The acquisition of language proficiency is significantly influenced by formal education. Educational institutions offer structured language training, opportunities for vocabulary development, instruction on grammatical principles, as well as sufficient opportunities for practice and constructive feed-

back. Furthermore, the language competency methodologies employed by teachers (Larsson, of children is greatly influenced by the teach- 2020). ing methods, curriculum design, and evaluation

Table 2: Post-Test Score of Pupils

Group	n	Mean	Rating	Descriptive Equivalent
Controlled Group				
Pre-test	46	23.5	52.2	Beginning
Post-test	46	33.8	75.1	Developing
Experimental Group				
Pre-test	45	30.5	67.8	Beginning
Post-test	45	39.3	87.3	Approaching Proficiency

Shown in table 2 are the post-test scores of the grade seven students. The controlled group got the mean of 33.8 or Developing while the experimental group gained the mean of 39.3 or Approaching Proficiency. It can be gleaned from the table that during post-test the experimental group has a higher mean rating over the controlled group. It got a mean rating increase of 8.8 from a mean rating of 30.5 to 39.3. This means that experimental group has a far better performance than the controlled group. This finding is congruent to the idea of Woodrow (2020) who cited that numerous study have been conducted to examined the impact of language proficiency on academic success. The findings of the study revealed a strong connection between language proficiency and academic achievement. A high level of lan-

guage proficiency is crucial for comprehending the subject matter, engaging in classroom discourse, and writing research papers. There is a positive correlation between higher levels of linguistic proficiency among students and their academic performance across various subjects (Woodrow, 2020). The development of language proficiency does not come without of problems. Individuals engaged in the process of learning may encounter challenges pertaining to the accurate pronunciation of sounds, grammatical structures, the acquisition of vocabulary terms, as well as the comprehension and application of cultural nuances. Language proficiency growth can be hindered by sociocultural issues, including discrimination and limited access to resources (Hakuta, 2020).

Table 3: Test on the Significant Difference between the Pre-Test and Post-Test Score

Test	df	t-value	p-value	Test Remarks
Pre-test and Post-test	39	-5.36	.0344	Significant

Table 3 shows the test on the significant difference between the pretest and post-test score of the respondents. It registered a t-value of -

5.36 with a p-value of .0344 which is lesser than .05 level of significance which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest

scores and the post test scores of the grade seven students. This implies that the used of oral language development and language proficiency among grade seven students contributed the effectiveness in teaching the subject which is revealed by the scores of the grade seven students. This finding is in line with the statement of Pokay (2020) who said that the effective ways for developing language proficiency have been established by researchers and educators. Some examples of effective language learning strategies include immersive language programs, language exchanges, substantial read-

ing and writing exercises, active engagement with authentic materials, and the utilization of digital resources and language learning applications (Pokay, 2020). Numerous factors contribute to language proficiency. One factor is the exposure to language. The quantity and quality of language exposure have a substantial influence on an individual’s level of language proficiency. Frequent exposure to oral and written language through various forms of communication, literary resources, and multimedia aids in the cultivation of vocabulary, grammar, and comprehension proficiencies (Fuchsen, 2019).

Table 4: Test on the Magnitude of Difference between the Pretest and Post test Scores of the Grade seven students

N	t-value	Eta2	Descriptive Value	Decision
91	-4.36	0.440	Large Effect	Relatively Adapt

Table 4 highlights the test of oral language development and language proficiency approach on the language development of grade seven students. It generated an Eta2 value of 0.440 which signifies large effect. By adopting these strategies, teachers can create a learning environment that is both engaging and effective, fostering improved oral language development and language proficiency among grade seven students. This strategy and combine practical application, interdisciplinary content, and interactive learning, teachers can enhance both oral language development and overall language proficiency among grade seven students. The language proficiency

of individuals can be influenced by various factors within the educational setting, such as the quality of the environment, teaching methodologies employed, availability of resources, and level of assistance provided. The enhancement of language skills can be facilitated by the utilization of engaging and interactive language education, provision of access to different learning materials, and the presence of supportive teachers. Effective language curriculum, proficient instructors, and suitable learning materials have the potential to enhance language development (Alderson, 2020).

4. Conclusions and Recommendations

This chapter displays the summary of the findings, conclusions and recommendations drawn out by the researcher after the analysis and interpretation of the findings had been made. This study sought to determine the effect of oral language development and language proficiency among grade seven students. This study made use of quasi-experimental research design, which is a non-equivalent control group pretest-posttest design. Non-equivalent design is a good design when the researcher has access to one group for experimentation (Vockel 1983). The researcher opted to use this design because the subjects of the study are intact group of learners. This study

was conducted in Sta. Cruz National School, Sta Cruz South District, Division of Davao Del Sur. The subjects of this study will be the 91 grade seven students – 46 are from section A which will be the controlled group and 45 are from section B which will be the experimental group. The composition of these two sections is homogeneous. Both learners from sections A and B have identical grades. This study makes use of the non-random assignment of subjects where all learners of both sections A and B are involved as subjects of the study.

This study revealed that the use of oral language development and language proficiency has increased the language competency of seventh-grade students. It also revealed that there is magnitude of difference between the post test scores of the controlled and experimental groups.

4.1. Conclusions—Based on the collective findings on this study, the following conclusions are drawn: The pre-test scores of the grade seven students both the controlled and experimental groups is at the Beginning level. The post-test scores of the controlled group is at the Developing level while the post test scores of the experimental group is at the Approaching level.

4.2. Recommendations—In the light of the findings drawn out by the researcher in this study, the following recommendations are offered: It is recommended that teachers teaching grade seven students should use oral language development and language proficiency as a strategy that would further develop different aspects of the teaching and learning process. In teaching, oral language development and language proficiency are fundamental aspects of a student’s educational journey, especially for those in grade seven. This stage marks a critical period in their academic and personal growth, where the ability to articulate thoughts, engage in discussions, and comprehend complex texts becomes increasingly important. The school heads should promote the use of oral language development and language proficiency among grade seven students as a strategy that would engage the child actively in the learning process as it is revealed in the study that the use of oral language development and language proficiency has increased the language competency of seventh-grade students. Oral language development and language proficiency integral to the success of grade seven students. These skills underpin academic achievement, cognitive development, and social interactions. By fostering a language-rich environment, incorporating effective teaching strategies, and encouraging meaningful conversations, educators and parents can support students in developing strong oral language skills and achieving language proficiency. This foundation will not only enhance their performance in grade seven but also set them on a path toward lifelong learning and success. A school policy about the utilization of role play can be issued. Besides, he can invite the teacher-researcher to demoteach during LAC session using play as a strategy in teaching. For future researchers, it is strongly recommended that a relative study on the use of oral language development and language proficiency as a strategy in teaching will be conducted. Another dimension in teaching can serve as another indicator.

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